

The Unjournal

Evaluation Summary and Metrics: "The Macroeconomic Impact of Climate Change: Global vs. Local Temperature"

Evaluator 1 Evaluator 2 Ben Balmford¹

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Published on: Jan 11, 2025

DOI: <https://doi.org/10.21428/d28e8e57.cd61ce83>

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ABSTRACT

We organized two evaluations of the paper: "The Macroeconomic Impact of Climate Change: Global vs. Local Temperature"^[1]. The paper offers a new approach to estimating the damages of climate change, and their results suggest a substantially higher social cost of carbon. The evaluators are highly positive about nearly all aspects of this work, while offering concrete suggestions for further improvement. To read these evaluations, please see the links below.

Evaluations

1. [Evaluator 1](#)

2. [Evaluator 2](#)

Overall ratings

We asked evaluators to provide overall assessments as well as ratings for a range of specific criteria.

I. Overall assessment (See footnote¹)

II. Journal rank tier, normative rating (0-5): On a 'scale of journals', what 'quality of journal' should this be published in?² *Note: 0= lowest/none, 5= highest/best.*

	Overall assessment (0-100)	Journal rank tier, normative rating (0-5)
Evaluator 1	85	4.5
Evaluator 2	90	4.7

See "[Metrics](#)" below for a more detailed breakdown of the evaluators' ratings across several categories. To see these ratings in the context of all Unjournal ratings, with some analysis, see our [data presentation here](#).³

See [here](#) for the current full evaluator guidelines, including further explanation of the requested ratings.

Evaluation summaries

Anonymous evaluator 1

If I were reviewing this manuscript for an economics journal, I would recommend revise and resubmit, with only minor revisions. Overall, the manuscript is well written in the sense that, since the reader understands immediately what is being estimated and why, that they could be lulled into the trap of thinking that the

research is "obvious." The final line before the conclusion is "We conclude that climate change poses a substantial threat to the world economy." But it is the careful empirical construction of the argument, and the identification that a literature has been mechanically missing (netting out) the effect of global temperature shocks while focussing exclusively on local temperature shocks, that gives this manuscript its evident worth.

The manuscript consists of two parts. First, a reduced form impact of global temperature shocks on economic activity at the world and country level. Second, a structural model to convert those estimates into welfare losses and a valuation of the social cost of carbon. The first is the "heart" of the paper in my estimation, while the second half is where many articles stop short - the "so what."

Anonymous evaluator 2

The paper's empirical innovation is simple: estimating the impacts of temperature on GDP using global time-series data, implicitly capturing the relationship between global temperatures, extreme events, and GDP without modelling all intermediate pathways. This idea, combined with their rigorous analytic approach, may have far-reaching implications due to the huge magnitude of the resulting estimates.

Given the small sample size used to estimate their main results ($N < 60$), robustness checks and cautious inference are essential. I recommend additional checks, which may increase their uncertainty estimates, and could result in either higher or lower estimated impacts.

Metrics

Ratings

[See here](#) for details on the categories below, and the guidance given to evaluators.

	Evaluator 1			Evaluator 2		
	Anonymous			Anonymous		
Rating category	Rating (0-100)	90% CI (0-100)*	Comments	Rating (0-100)	90% CI (0-100)*	Comments
Overall assessment ⁴	85	(80, 90)	5	90	(80, 100)	6
Claims, strength, characterization of evidence ⁷	85	(75, 95)	8	92	(85, 100)	

Advancing knowledge and practice ⁹	90	(89, 91)	10	98	(95, 100)	
Methods: Justification, reasonableness, validity, robustness ¹¹	80	(70, 90)	12	88	(75, 100)	13
Logic & communication 14	85	(75, 95)	15	100	(100, 100)	16
Open, collaborative, replicable ¹⁷	25	(10, 40)	18	100	(100, 100)	19
Real-world relevance 20, 21	85	(80, 90)		95	(90, 100)	22
Relevance to global priorities ^{23, 24}	85	(80, 90)		95	(90, 100)	

Journal ranking tiers

[See here](#) for more details on these tiers.

	Evaluator 1 Anonymous			Evaluator 2 Anonymous	
Judgment	Ranking tier (0-5)	90% CI	Comments	Ranking tier (0-5)	90% CI
On a 'scale of journals', what 'quality of journal' <i>should</i> this be published in?	4.5	(4.0, 5.0)		4.7	(4.5, 5.0)

What 'quality journal' do you expect this work <i>will</i> be published in?	4.5	(4.0, 5.0)	25	4.7	(4.5, 5.0)
See here for more details on these tiers.	<p><i>We summarize these as:</i></p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • 0.0: Marginally respectable/Little to no value • 1.0: OK/Somewhat valuable • 2.0: Marginal B-journal/Decent field journal • 3.0: Top B-journal/Strong field journal • 4.0: Marginal A-Journal/Top field journal • 5.0: A-journal/Top journal 				

Evaluation manager's discussion (Ben Balmford)

This paper represents a step-change in how the damages of climate change are estimated empirically. Rather than relying solely on *local* temperature shocks, this paper is able to determine the negative consequences of *global* temperature shocks, which drastically increases the estimated Social Cost of Carbon. From a policy perspective, this implies that measures to mitigate climate change are even more likely to be welfare-enhancing and are more urgently needed.

Both evaluators provide extremely positive reports on the quality and likely impact of the paper. It clearly makes a very large and important contribution to the literature. The evaluators propose ways to enhance the paper's impact with relatively small changes.

In addition to these revisions to the main paper, I'd suggest the authors also write a synopsis for laypeople – explaining in simple terms the advances the paper makes and the key results it offers that should influence future policy.

Both evaluations, particularly the second, offer numerous – but very do-able – changes which would further enhance the academic quality of what is already a very impressive paper. Finally, in terms of replicability/open science, while evaluator 2 rightly recognises that having a replication package available pre-publication is very good (and unusual), evaluator 1's remark regarding its completeness is correct.

Process notes

The authors were offered the opportunity to respond to these evaluations, but they declined.

References

1. Bilal, A., & Känzig, D. R. (2024). The Macroeconomic Impact of Climate Change: Global vs. Local Temperature. NBER Working Paper 32450. <https://doi.org/10.3386/w32450>

Footnotes

1. We asked them to rank this paper “heuristically” as a percentile “relative to all serious research in the same area that you have encountered in the last three years.” We requested they “consider all aspects of quality, credibility, importance to knowledge production, and importance to practice. [↵](#)

2. See ranking tiers discussed [here](#). [↵](#)

3. Note: if you are reading this before, or soon after this has been publicly released, the ratings from this paper may not yet have been incorporated into that data presentation. [↵](#)

4.

Judge the quality of the research heuristically. Consider all aspects of quality, credibility, importance to knowledge production, and importance to practice.

[↵](#)

5. A careful capstone or next step for a mature and important literature [↵](#)

6. Possibly hugely influential, as long as the findings are robust. I think they are likely to be robust, but that some more checks are necessary [↵](#)

7. “Do the authors do a good job of (i) stating their main questions and claims, (ii) providing strong evidence and powerful approaches to inform these, and (iii) correctly characterizing the nature of their evidence?”

This was on the newer form only [↵](#)

8. See my primary request. [↵](#)

9.

To what extent does the project contribute to the field or to practice, particularly in ways that are directly or indirectly relevant to global priorities and impactful interventions?

[↵](#)

10. The better assessment of a social cost of carbon is a first-order problem for humanity, with strong downstream effects through the policy process. [↵](#)

11. Are methods clearly justified and explained? Are methods and their underlying assumptions reasonable? Are the results likely to be robust to changes in the assumptions? Have the authors avoided bias and questionable research practices? [↔](#)

12. [↔](#)

13. Are methods clearly justified and explained? Are methods and their underlying assumptions reasonable and appropriate? Are the results likely to be robust to changes in the assumptions? Have the authors avoided bias and questionable research practices? [↔](#)

14. Are concepts clearly defined? Is the reasoning transparent? Are conclusions consistent with the evidence (or formal proofs) presented? Are the data and/or analysis, including tables and figures, relevant to the argument? [↔](#)

15. The concepts are clearly defined and reasoning is first-rate. The nature of the evidence is detailed, for a sophisticated reader perfectly explained. [↔](#)

16. Very clearly written [↔](#)

17.

Would another researcher be able to replicate the analysis? Are the method and its details explained sufficiently? Is the source of the data clear? Is the data made as widely available as possible, with clear labeling and explanation? Do the authors provide resources that are likely to enable future research and meta-analysis?

[↔](#)

18. The current replication is incomplete, does not cover all of the analysis (e.g. no panel estimations), and is far from comprehensive. Hopefully the authors offer a full replication package in time. [↔](#)

19. Data sets are all public and clearly described. Replication code for the key results has been made public on Github ahead of publication, which is great and very transparent. [↔](#)

20.

Does the paper consider real-world relevance and deal with policy and implementation questions? Are the setup, assumptions, and focus realistic and relevant to practitioners?

[↔](#)

21.

The latter ratings were merged in the newer form

"Are the paper's chosen topic and approach likely to be useful to global priorities, cause prioritization, and high-impact interventions?"

"Does the paper consider real-world relevance and deal with policy and implementation questions? Are the setup, assumptions, and focus realistic? Do the authors report results that are relevant to practitioners? Do they provide useful quantified estimates (costs, benefits, etc.)?" [↵](#)

22. Extremely relevant to practitioners. Some more context on some of the results is warranted, especially around what the results don't capture (e.g.adaptation, possibility of technological change, climate tipping points, and non-market damages), since this paper could be quite influential for policymakers. [↵](#)

23. Are the paper's chosen topic and approach likely to be useful to global priorities, cause prioritization, and high-impact interventions? [↵](#)

24.

The latter ratings were merged in the newer form

"Are the paper's chosen topic and approach likely to be useful to global priorities, cause prioritization, and high-impact interventions?"

"Does the paper consider real-world relevance and deal with policy and implementation questions? Are the setup, assumptions, and focus realistic? Do the authors report results that are relevant to practitioners? Do they provide useful quantified estimates (costs, benefits, etc.)?" [↵](#)

25. I use economics journals only in my estimation here. [↵](#)

References

1. Bilal, Adrien, and Diego Känzig. 'The Macroeconomic Impact of Climate Change: Global vs. Local Temperature'. Cambridge, MA: National Bureau of Economic Research, May 2024.
<https://doi.org/10.3386/w32450>. [↵](#)